

The Influence of Consumer Behavior, Perspectives and Types of Consumers in Purchasing Decision Making

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ABSTRACT: Purchasing or consumption can be said to be the main goal of consumer behavior. While purchases will occur because of the need and desire for the product. But not infrequently the purchase is not caused by a need and desire. Someone before making a purchase begins with a need and a desire (want). Buying activity is part of an effort to fulfill the urge of needs and desires. Need is a state that is felt not to exist in a person. Something that is not in a person. The experience decision-making perspective is carried out by consumers who have experience in understanding brands and products. For consumers, knowledge about brands and products is considered sufficient. So there is no need for a lot of information related to the use of brands and products. The influence of experience from using brands and products has an impact on the purchasing decision-making process. The introduction of the problem around how the experience of brand and product problems before. Information search process based on solving problems from previous purchases. Brand and product choices are based on the impact of previous experience. Consumer behavior in the purchasing decision process does not always follow a linear path in the consumption process. Linear flow in decision making starts from problem recognition, seeking information, evaluating information, purchasing, and evaluating after purchase. Because consumers have different attitudes and views on brands and products. There are several types of consumers based on consumer involvement. Consumer engagement with brands and products. Consumer involvement in assessing brand existence. It is a consumer effort to compare brands, loyalty to certain brands, even rejection of certain brands. Consumer involvement in a brand is a consumer evaluation of a brand that has been known and is being promoted by the seller.

KEYWORDS: Behavior, decision process, consumer type

I. CONSUMER BEHAVIOR

In our daily lives, we are never separated from buying a product. Either in relatively small amounts or in large quantities. Buying activities can be carried out by a person and organization. If the product purchased will be used alone is referred to as consumption. Meanwhile, if the product purchased is for the purposes of producing other products. Then the buying activity is said to be an investment activity. The definition of consumer behavior refers to activities related to the individual buying process. Quite a lot of explanations about consumer behavior. Among them according to Mowen and Minor (2002: 5), consumer behavior is the study of units and decision-making processes involved in receiving, using and determining goods, services, and ideas. This definition explains if consumer behavior as a purchasing decision-making process. Purchase decisions made by each individual or group related to the use and selection of products. Where the product can be in the form of goods or services. Meanwhile, according to Schiffman and Kanuk (1991:5) consumer behavior is the study of how individuals make decisions to use the resources they have on consumption related to products. Understanding consumer behavior leads to making purchasing decisions. As well as determine the budget available for the purchase decision. The budget allocation is important enough for consumers to pay attention to. because the budget is a factor that limits the amount that can be consumed. Meanwhile, according to Kotler (1997) consumer behavior as the final purchase behavior, individuals or households, buy products for personal consumption. Consumers are individuals who use products for their own interests. Not to be traded back like traders. Products purchased by consumers will be utilized by the consumer concerned. It is a manifestation of the use of the inherent function of the product. Meanwhile, according to Engel et al. (1995) Consumer behavior leads to actions to acquire, product consumption, and purchase decision processes. This definition shows consumer behavior as part of the act of buying a product, and the process after purchase. From several definitions of consumer behavior can be concluded. Consumer behavior is a number of activities related to buying and using products. Process before and after purchase decision.

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Purchasing or consumption can be said to be the main goal of consumer behavior. While purchases will occur because of the need and desire for the product. But not infrequently the purchase is not caused by a need and desire. For example, purchases because of prestige factors, or just a hobby or happy doing shopping activities. According to Kotler (1997) a person before making a purchase begins with a need and a desire. Buying activity is part of an effort to fulfill the urge of needs and desires. Need is a state that is felt not to exist in a person. Something that is not in a person. Suppose there is no feeling of satiety, then food is needed. Because everyone will feel hungry if they don't eat. Likewise with clothes place to live, and so on that is felt not to exist in a person. This condition creates a need. And there is a tendency if the needs of each individual are relatively the same. Meanwhile, want is a human need that is shaped by culture and individual personality. As a result, individual desires are relatively different, because they have been influenced by cultural and personality factors. So based on their needs, people who live in urban areas will certainly be different from those who live around the interior. As a result, individual desires are relatively different, because they have been influenced by cultural and personality factors. So based on their needs, people who live in urban areas will certainly be different from those who live around the interior. As a result, individual desires are relatively different, because they have been influenced by cultural and personality factors. So based on their needs, people who live in urban areas will certainly be different from those who live around the interior.

II. CONSUMER BEHAVIOR APPROACH

In studying consumer behavior there are several orientation approaches. Among them are economic theory approaches, psychological theory approaches, social and cultural theoretical approaches.

Economic Theory

The economic theory approach places more emphasis on the economic principles that humans do. This economic principle begins with minimal efforts to meet their needs to the fullest. With unlimited human needs. And the economic resources to meet those needs are limited. This is an economic problem. But it became the beginning of the development of economic theory. Part of economics is the theory of demand which explains the relationship between consumer demand for a product. And the factors that influence it. As well as the concept of maximum satisfaction from consuming the product (maximum utility).

Psychological Theory

Consumer behavior is part of the result of a person's psychological factors. Psychological factors lead to brand and product selection behavior. In psychological theory, there are learning theories and motivational theories.

Learning theory, explains if someone tends to carry out the learning process before and after doing something. When you are going to buy a product. Previously someone had studied the existence of these brands and products. Likewise, after using a product, someone tends to learn the benefits of the product. Learning theory was developed by psychologists such as Ivan Pavlov, Skinner and Hull. This theory is based on four main components, namely, drive, cue, response, and reinforcement. Drive is a situation that makes someone do something. Or there are strong stimuli in a person that forces him to act. Drive can be divided into physiological drives such as; hungry, thirst and encouragement that are the result of the learning process (learning drive), for example; scared, happy. Several theories that can explain consumer learning processes include stimulus response theory (stimulus and response theory). According to this theory the learning process is a response from a person to a stimulus that he faces. This stimulus-response theory also concludes if behavior is a positive or negative response. Stimulation and response theory is related to learner behavior theory and cognitive theory. In the theory of awareness the learning process is influenced by factors such as attitudes, beliefs, past experiences, awareness of how to take advantage of a situation to achieve goals. Form and field theory (Gestalt and Field Theory) This theory looks at the learning process and behavior as a whole. This theory is based on experiments that prove that individual stimuli are received and interpreted based on past experiences. The process of observation, past experience, and goal setting are the determinants of behavior. As an illustration of a person who is going to buy a car, before deciding to buy, of course that person will study the specifications of the car, the advantages and disadvantages of the car. As well as studying the conditions that are not expected from the car. Such as damage or interference with the car engine. Likewise, when deciding to buy a car, the consumer will learn all the information about the whereabouts of the car, where it is sold, price, and ease of purchase financing. Then after a car purchase occurs, the buyer continues to carry out the learning process related to the evaluation after experiencing the car. Such as learning about the possibility of an insurance claim if an unexpected incident occurs from the car, and learning how to get access to service after purchase. The learning process is mostly carried out by someone who is new to the brand and product being purchased. However, the learning process is also carried out by consumers who already know brands and products. Learning is done to better understand the development of quality and benefits of brands and products. the buyer continues to carry out the learning process related to the evaluation after feeling the car. Such as learning about the possibility of an insurance claim if an unexpected incident occurs from the car, and learning how to get access to service after purchase. The learning process is mostly carried out by someone

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The theory of motivation, before carrying out activities is often preceded by a certain encouragement that results in carrying out these activities. The urge to do something with awareness is part of a form of motivation. According to Schiffman & Kanuk (2000), motivation is explained as the force that drives individuals to act. This drive results from a pressure that arises due to unmet needs. Meanwhile, according to Solomon (1999), motivation is a process that causes a person to act as he does. This happens when he expects satisfaction. When a need has been met, it will encourage consumers to reduce that need. From this definition it can be concluded that motivation is a stimulus that drives a person to act, cooperate, work effectively, and integrated to achieve the expected goals. Among the goals of doing something is getting answers to needs and wants. Among the motivational theories that are quite popular is Maslow's motivation theory (Maslow's Motive Hierarchy). A person as well as an organization cannot escape the need. Because the existence of a need indicates that there are activities that support the ongoing life. Needs continue to grow in accordance with the development of human prosperity. As described in the theory of motivation. According to Maslow's theory of needs, individual or group needs can be divided into several levels or levels of needs. The most basic level as physiological needs (physiological). For example the need for food, drink, shelter. The next level is the need for safety For example, the need for health, comfort, security. Followed by the need for a sense of belonging (belongingness) such as the need for socialization, friends, ownership, affection. The need for recognition (esteem) includes the need for status, self-esteem, or prestige. While the highest level of self-actualization needs, including the need for development and self-realization. Based on the theory of motivation, it shows that a person fulfills his needs according to his abilities. Thus each level is an increase of needs. While the highest level of self-actualization needs, including the need for development and self-realization. Based on the theory of motivation, it shows that a person fulfills his needs according to his abilities. Thus each level is an increase of needs. While the highest level of self-actualization needs, including the need for development and self-realization. Based on the theory of motivation, it shows that a person fulfills his needs according to his abilities. Thus each level is an increase of needs.

Consumption Decision

What will you do when you have a vacation plan to the island of Bali. What preparations should be made. So that travel plans run smoothly. As well as in accordance with the plan to get a fun vacation form. Of course there must be careful planning and preparation related to these holiday needs. Planning and preparation are matters that lead to a goal. It is the same with consumers before getting a product which is expected to face a series of problems related to the product. The series of problems is part of the existence of cause and effect and the use of the product. Why do consumers need a product and what is the process that follows when they get the product. As well as the process that will occur after obtaining the desired product. According to Kotler and Amstrong (1992) there are a series of activities carried out when consumers make a purchase (consumer purchase decision process). The series of activities includes problem recognition, gathering information (information search), evaluation of alternative information (evaluation of alternatives), purchase (purchase decision), and behavior after purchase (post purchase behavior).

The buying decision-making process begins with a problem (problem recognition). The problem is a motivating factor to do something. Consumer problems related to the existence of needs and desires for brands and products. When someone is going to travel to a place that is considered far away. So you need a means of transportation to reach the place.

The existence of a need and desire for a brand and product leads to an information search (information search) about brands and products. Information search and collection can be obtained from brand and product providers, for example from promotional information. But information can also be obtained from other parties, such as from fellow consumers, or references from other parties. Media providers of information today are quite a lot and varied. In line with advances in information

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technology, such as television, the internet. Of course very helpful consumers in getting information. Information that supports problem solving.

The next step in the consumption decision process is to conduct an evaluation of alternative information (evaluation of alternatives). The information that has been collected will be evaluated based on the level of need and importance. The resulting evaluation is in the form of several alternative information needed. Because it does not require all the information that has been obtained to be used all. Purchasing (purchase decision), is the most important part of the results of purchasing decisions. Purchasing activities include the time of purchase, location of purchase, type of product, product alternatives selected.

After the purchase is made, it is followed by post-purchase behavior. The occurrence of product purchases does not mean that consumers do not continue the purchase decision process. After purchasing, consumers will evaluate the products they have purchased. Evaluation after purchase results in conclusions regarding the continuation of consumption of the product. If the consumer gives a good assessment of the product. So it is an early indication of satisfaction. So it is possible that there will be a repeat purchase. Meanwhile, if the consumer's assessment gives doubt to the product. Of course consumers will reconsider the use of the product. But if the consumer gives a bad product rating, because the product is considered not to give satisfaction.

Does the consumer follow a linear step in the consumption decision-making process. From several purchase cases, not all steps of the decision process are used by consumers. especially if consumers are very familiar with brands and products. As well as having undergone periodic purchases and in a relatively long time. But that does not mean that the linear consumption decision-making process is no longer used by consumers. According to Mowen and Minor (2002) there are several perspectives on decision making. Among them are traditional decision-making perspectives including low involvement decisions (low involvement decisions) and high involvement decisions (high involvement decisions), experience decision making perspectives (experiential perspective), and behavioral influence perspectives (behavior influence perspective).

When consumers make purchases follow the stages in the decision-making process. Starting from recognizing the problem, gathering information, evaluating information, buying, and evaluating after purchase. Shows if the consumer uses a traditional decision-making perspective. In the traditional perspective, there are two possible buying decision processes. Consumers do with low involvement (low involvement decision). This means that consumers simplify the decision process. The decision process is carried out with little involvement in brand and product choices. The definition of involvement shows the role and interest of consumers in brands and types of products. Low involvement shows that consumers pay less attention to brands and types of products. On the other hand, high involvement means that consumers pay attention to the existence of brands and various types of products for consideration. Low involvement decision making depends on the level of recognition of the brand and product. Increasingly known brands and products decision-making process is done with low involvement. Product prices also influence decisions in a low-involvement manner. Products with low prices purchase decision process is simpler than expensive products.

Purchase decision process with high involvement (high involvement decision). High engagement with brand considerations and product considerations. Consumers will carry out an evaluation process before deciding to purchase. Starting from in-depth problem identification, collecting extensive brand and product information. Evaluate the choice of information in detail. Make purchases with brand comparisons as well as product comparisons. With the evaluation process after the purchase is carried out in depth.

The experience decision-making perspective is carried out by consumers who have experience in understanding brands and products. For consumers, knowledge about brands and products is considered sufficient. So there is no need for a lot of information related to the use of brands and products. The influence of experience from using brands and products has an impact on the purchasing decision-making process. So when the next purchase is made it is part of the improvement of the previous purchase. So consumers will be more observant about brands and products. The introduction of the problem around how the experience of brand and product problems before. Information search process based on solving problems from previous purchases. Alternative evaluation is a comparison process from experiences about brands and products.

The behavioral influence perspective places more emphasis on consumer behavior factors. so that the decision-making process is more likely to be influenced by consumer behavior. The introduction of the problem basing on the characteristics of consumer behavior. between one consumer and another consumer there is a difference in understanding brand and product issues. Search for more information on responses that have been studied. With an alternative evaluation that is more the result of behavior than self-empowerment. Meanwhile, brand and product choices are controlled by consumer perceptions.

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Consumer Type

Consumer behavior in the purchasing decision process does not always follow a linear path in the consumption process. Linear flow in decision making starts from problem recognition, seeking information, evaluating information, purchasing, and evaluating after purchase. Because consumers have different attitudes and views on brands and products. According to Mowen there are several types of consumers based on consumer involvement. Consumer engagement with brands and products. Consumer involvement in assessing brand existence. It is a consumer effort to compare brands, loyalty to certain brands, even rejection of certain brands. Consumer involvement in a brand is a consumer evaluation of a brand that has been known and is being promoted by the seller. While consumer involvement in the product is part of the form of evaluation on product quality, product physical form, product benefits, and product ease of use. The high involvement form indicates if the attention to the brand and product is high. Meanwhile, low involvement indicates low attention to brands and products or less attention. Here are several types of consumers based on involvement in brands and products.

Complex buying behavior is a form of consumer behavior that is high in brand involvement. Consumers do not simply compare brands but also look for the many alternative brands available. And involvement in the product is also high, meaning that consumers are more careful in looking for the advantages and disadvantages of the product. Starting from packaging, price, benefits, services, and supporting product specifications (Nirwana, 2006). Usually this complex behavior is carried out by consumers who will consume goods with high economic value. Like buying a luxury car, apartment, or going on a trip with a high budget. However, it is possible that consumer characteristic factors also determine complex buying behavior.

Variety seeking buying behavior (Buying behavior that seeks diversity), this behavior leads to low involvement in the product, but high involvement in the brand. This is intended to get a variety of alternative brands. Or try the existence of a brand that has not been known so far. Consumers tend to pay less attention to the product, the physical form of the product, the benefits of the product, and the ease of use of the product. This condition indicates that consumers want to try several brands. Consumed products tend to be products with low economic value. Such as bath soap, wall paint, household items with low economic value, perfumes and electrical equipment.

Dissonance reducing buying behavior, this type of buyer tends to be high in product involvement. This is done to reduce product risk. Such as physical risk, time risk, financial risk, and product function risk. Meanwhile, brand involvement tends to be low. This means that consumers are not concerned with the existence of the brand. For this type of consumer the main interest is the existence of the product. The physical form of the product, the benefits of the product, and the ease of use of the product. An example of this type of consumer is purchasing products that are rarely used but have relatively expensive economic value. Such as buying household furniture, carpets, ceramics, and also buying fences for houses.

Habitual buying behavior (buying behavior based on habits), part of the buying behavior that is often done by consumers in general. Consumers only need low involvement with the brand and also with the product. For consumers, the existence of a brand is very well known, or vice versa, it is not important to know it. Because what matters to consumers is the benefits of the product. While involvement in the product is low. Reflecting that the product is often used in everyday life. So it's enough to emphasize the function and benefits of the product. This type of purchase occurs for products with relatively cheap economic value. And the nature of the product is necessary in daily activities.

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